

A Comprehensive Study of Crowd-Sourced Phishing Submission Dynamics: Trends, Patterns, and Insights for Effective Countermeasures.

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Abstract

This study aims to analyse recurrent patterns in phishing submissions within a global phishing reporting community, with a focus on understanding the evolution of phishing activities over time. The research investigates key aspects such as trends in valid and invalid phishing submissions, seasonal peaks in phishing activity, and correlations between submissions and verification time. The study seeks to determine if there are significant differences between valid and invalid phishing submissions, and the potential influence of specific months on phishing occurrences, offering valuable insights for future interventions. The research will also examine the features of phishing datasets, and the application of statistical and machine learning methodologies to detect patterns that can enhance the effectiveness of anti-phishing initiatives.

Keywords: phishing, k-means, silhouette score, clustering, quishing

1.0 Introduction

Phishing is a recurrent social engineering incursion aimed at eliciting sensitive information from unsuspecting users by mimicking a legitimate or trustworthy entity (Nieles et al., 2017). According to the FBI Internet Crime Report 2020, Phishing “as of 2020, phishing is the most recurrent kind of cybercrime” (FBI Internet Crime Report, 2020).

The prevalent nature of phishing attacks might be due to the nominal cost of launching the attack and its high effectiveness (Davies, 2024). The utilisation of numerous attack methods increases the likelihood of success. Attack vectors utilised by phishers include QR code scams, man-in-the-browser (MitB) attacks, cloned websites, and embedding malicious links or attachments in phony emails and text messages (Gautam et al., 2021). Phishing techniques are constantly changing, with deceptive communications closely resembling the original, and it is increasingly difficult for organisations and individuals to identify, combat, or prevent phishing attacks (Alnemari, 2023).

The continuously evolving strategies employed by phishers necessitate a persistent effort to remain aware of emerging threats and to uphold strong security measures. Additionally, organisations and businesses would need to leverage advanced security software, machine learning algorithms, and artificial intelligence tools to identify and isolate phishing attempts before they become mainstream on the internet.

Addressing phishing effectively requires a comprehensive strategy that integrates technological advancements, educational initiatives for users, and collaborative intelligence efforts. Efficient global phishing reporting communities can be distinguished by these characteristics:

- They are community-driven and powered by an ecosystem of users who submit and verify phishing sites. This crowdsourced approach helps to ensure the data is timely and accurate.
- They are open and accessible. Data is freely available for download or through APIs, making it a valuable resource for researchers, developers, and anyone interested in fighting phishing.
- Regular database updates with new submissions when discovered. The community actively participates in this process, ensuring the database remains current and relevant.

The purpose of the study is to comprehensively analyse recurrent statistics related to phishing submissions and understand the following:

- How do phishing submissions, including valid phishing and invalid phishing submissions evolve over time?
- Are there clear peaks in phishing activities? If yes, what might be the reasons for these spikes? Additionally, does the month of the year significantly affect the number of valid phishing counts?
- Is there a significant relationship between the number of valid phishing submissions and the total time spent verifying them?
- Is there a significant difference between the periodic counts of valid phishing submissions and invalid phishing submissions?
- What other patterns can be derived from aggregated phishing data related to help proffer data-driven recommendations for effectively combating phishing attacks?

2.0 Literature Review

Phishing has a negative effect on both individual and corporate targets. It is appropriate to examine the current methods employed in phishing attacks in detail (Chiew et.al. 2018). Common phishing methods include spear phishing, a more focused phishing attack that employs personalised communication, particularly through emails (Bossetta, 2018). Voice phishing, or vishing, utilises Voice over IP (VoIP) technology in its attacks. Victims are prompted to provide sensitive information or are connected to a live operator who employs social engineering techniques to extract information (Choi, et.al., 2015).

Fraudsters can take advantage of the ease of use associated with QR codes to deceive individuals into disclosing sensitive information. This is referred to as quishing. As the use of QR codes expands for purposes such as payments, event check-ins, and product information, quishing is becoming a notable concern in the field of digital security (Amoah & Hayfron-Acquah, 2022). SMS phishing, commonly referred to as smishing, is a form of phishing attack that employs text messages sent from mobile phones or smartphones to convey a deceptive message (Mishra & Soni, 2019).

Collaborative initiatives for phishing detection represent a strategic approach to flagging and reporting attempts. Examples of collaborative community efforts dedicated to combating phishing include security research communities, academic/research communities, and crowd-sourced global phishing reporting communities such as PhishTank (Saravanan & Subramanian, 2020).

While PhishTank, a crowd sourced anti-phishing community provides data regarding phishing scams, it depends on contributions from internet users who report websites they believe may be engaged in phishing activities. These reported sites undergo evaluation by fellow community members, who cast votes to indicate their agreement or disagreement regarding the site's classification as a phishing scam. This collective voting mechanism serves to enhance the reliability of the information gathered. Apart from verifying phishing data, Phishtank also offers the following services:

- Maintains a database of phishing sites: The verified phishing sites are added to PhishTank's database and this database is constantly updated with new phishing sites as they are discovered.
- Data to corporate organisations: Various anti-phishing organisations, including OpenDNS use PhishTank's data, to help protect users from phishing attacks. These

services use the data to block access to known phishing sites, and improve phishing detection systems.

- API for developers: PhishTank provides an API that developers can use to access their data and integrate phishing information into customised applications and services (Phishtank, 2006).
- Voting on submissions: Community stakeholders can verify the accuracy of PhishTank's data by voting on other users' submissions.

PhishTank plays a crucial role in the fight against phishing by providing a valuable source of information about phishing scams. Its community-driven approach and open access to data make it an essential tool for protecting internet users from these attacks.

3.0 Methodology

The first step was to extract aggregated data from PhishTank (<https://phishtank.org/>) using a web browser extension. A total of 101 records were extracted and assigned to related columns (PhishTank, 2025). The data was also pre-processed to ensure duplication, errors and inconsistencies were eliminated.

Regarding feature selection for modelling, the focus was on key quantitative features that reflect phishing activity. Tools and techniques for analysis were implemented via statistical and mathematical techniques using Python libraries and packages. The integrated development environment for executing the codes is Google Colabs.

Feature Name	Description
Phishing Data Month Year	Month/Year of aggregated phishing data
Total Submissions	Total phishing reports submitted
Valid Phishing	Confirmed phishing attempts This is the total number of submissions verified as valid by the PhishTank community
Invalid Phishing	Total number of submissions verified as invalid
Total Votes	Total number of votes made by phishing community
Total Time Verify Minutes	Median time spent verifying submissions in minutes
Phishing IP	Top IP address associated with phishing attempt
Phishing Domain	Top domain name used in phishing attempt
Top Network Host	Top Network
Network Phishing Amount	Phishing from the top network hosting verified phishes
Top Phishing Target	Top target of phishing attempt
Target Phishing Amount	Number of valid phishes associated with top target

Table 1.0 Phishing Dataset Description

Year	Total Valid Submissions	Median Time Taken (Minutes)
2009	92,074	16,230
2010	117,102	3,865
2011	164,917	2,093
2012	215,804	1,931
2013	294,308	5,993
2014	273,148	18,355
2015	289,004	71,429
2016	180,528	234,600
2017 ¹	40,326	102,822

Table 2.0 Valid Submission and Median Time Taken Aggregates for 2009-2017

Fig 1.0 Chart of Valid Submission & Median Time Taken Aggregates for 2009-2017

¹ Data related to 2017 was available for January to May only.

Year	Average Total Submissions	Average Valid Phishing Submissions	Average Invalid Phishing Submissions
2009	23,969	7,672	540
2010	16,341	10,010	561
2011	19,859	13,668	638
2012	28,796	18,502	1,380
2013	41,802	24,024	1,041
2014	56,797	24,799	972
2015	69,817	24,963	433
2016	79,586	15,367	409
2017	62,886	8,065	449

Table 3.0 Yearly Evolution Observation

- **Total Submissions Trend:** Steady increase from 2009 (23,969) to 2016 (79,586), peaking in 2016. Growth nearly triples over 8 years, reflecting rising phishing reports or awareness.
- **Valid Phishing Submissions Trend:** Rises from 2009 (7,672) to 2013 (24,024), peaks in 2015 (24,963), then drops sharply in 2016 (15,367) and 2017 (8,065).
- **Invalid Phishing Submissions Trend:** Gradual rise from 2009 (540) to 2012 (1,380), peaks in 2013 (1,041), then declines to 2016 (409).

3.1. Correlation Analysis Relationship between Valid Phishing Submissions and Verification Time

- **Question:** Is there a significant relationship between the total number of valid phishing submissions ("Valid_Phishing") and the total time spent verifying them ("Total_Median_Time_To_Verify")?
- **Hypothesis:**
 - H_0 : There is no correlation between "Valid_Phishing" and "Total_Median_Time_To_Verify" ($r = 0$).
 - H_1 : There is a correlation ($r \neq 0$).

- **Methodology:** Pearson correlation coefficient (r), measures the linear relationship between two continuous variables. Values range from -1 (perfect negative) to 1 (perfect positive), with 0 indicating no correlation. We calculate r using:

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Where $x = \text{Valid_Phishing}$, $y = \text{Total_Time_Verify_Minutes}$, and, \bar{x} , \bar{y} are means.

- **Results:**
 - **Pearson's Correlation:** ≈ -0.2351 . This value indicates a weak negative linear relationship. This means that, very generally, as the number of "Valid_Phishing" increases, the "Total_Median_Time_To_Verify" tends to decrease slightly.
 - **P-value:** ≈ 0.0185 . The p-value is less than 0.05, meaning the correlation is statistically significant. This infers the correlation that was found, unlikely to occur by random chance.
 - **Summary:** $r \approx -0.2527$, p-value ≈ 0.0156 (assuming $n = 100$). There is a statistically significant, weak negative linear relationship between the two variables. We are unable to dismiss the null hypothesis, H_0 , based on the available data. Initially, more valid phishing submissions might increase verification time, but later, verification time surges despite fewer valid cases (suggesting process changes or challenges). Even though there is a statistically significant link, the number of phishing results doesn't strongly predict the verification time.

3.2 Do Valid and Invalid Phishing Submissions Differ Significantly?

- **Question:** Is there a significant difference between the monthly counts of "Valid_Phishing" and "Invalid_Phishing"?
- **Hypothesis:**
 - H_0 : Mean difference between Valid_Phishing and Invalid_Phishing = 0 ($\mu d = 0$).
 - H_1 : Mean difference $\neq 0$ ($\mu d \neq 0$).

- **Methodology:** Paired T-Test, since these are paired observations from the same months.

$$t = \frac{\bar{d}}{s_d/\sqrt{n}}$$

Where $d = \text{Valid_Phishing} - \text{Invalid_Phishing}$, \bar{d} = mean difference, s_d = standard deviation of differences, $n = 100$.

- **Results:**
 - **T-statistic:** ≈ 18.9979 . In this instance, the large absolute value of the t-statistic indicates a substantial difference between the means. In this case, 18.99 is quite large, suggesting a strong difference.
 - **P-value:** $\approx 8.62e-35$ (8.62×10^{-35}). The very small p-value indicates that it's highly unlikely the observed difference occurred by chance alone.
 - **Mean Difference:** *Mean of Valid_Phishing:* 16672.11, *Mean of Invalid_Phishing:* 733.47. There is a significant difference between the two means.
 - **95% Confidence Interval of the difference:** (14273.94, 17603.339). This interval provides a range of values within which we are 95% confident that the true difference between the means of "Valid_Phishing" and "Invalid_Phishing" lies. The entire interval is positive and far from zero, it reinforces the conclusion there's a substantial and statistically significant difference. It means that on average, "Valid_Phishing" is between 14273.94 and 17603.33 higher than "Invalid_Phishing".

These outcomes strongly indicate that the number of "Valid_Phishing" occurrences is significantly higher than the number of "Invalid_Phishing" occurrences in the dataset. The extremely small p-value, the large t-statistic, the large difference in means, and the positive confidence interval all point to this conclusion. We reject the null hypothesis, H_0 .

3.3 Increase in Total Submissions over time?

- **Question:** Is there a significant Increase in Total Submissions over time?
- **Hypothesis:**
 - H_0 : No trend (significant increase) in Total_Submissions over time (slope = 0).

- H_1 : Positive trend (slope > 0).
- **Methodology**: Linear regression, with “Total_Submissions” as the dependent variable (y), and the time (month number, 1 to 101) as the independent variable (x)

$$y = bx + a$$

Where y = dependent variable = slope, a = intercept and x = independent variable

$$b = \frac{n \sum (x_i y_i) - \sum x_i \sum y_i}{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2}$$

And test significance:

$$t = \frac{b}{SE_b}$$

- **Results**
 - **Slope**: ≈ 731.2976 . The slope is positive, indicating a positive linear relationship. Over time, the total number of submissions tends to increase.
 - **T-statistic**: 16.4080. This is high, indicating the slope is statistically significant, suggesting a strong linear relationship between Month_Year and Total_Submissions.
 - **P-value**: ≈ 0.00 (effectively zero, indicating strong significance). A p-value of 0.0 (or very close to it) means there is an extremely low probability of observing the data if there were truly no relationship between "Month_Number" and "Total_Submissions." It signifies the slope is statistically significant. We can confidently reject the null hypothesis (the slope is zero).
 - **Summary**: This indicates that Total_Submissions (phishing reports) increase significantly over time. The large t-statistic and p-value indicate that this trend is not due to chance. We cannot accept the null hypothesis, H_0 .

3.4 Does Month Affect Valid Phishing?

- **Question**: Does the month of the year significantly affect "Valid_Phishing" counts?

- **Hypothesis:**
 - H_0 : No difference in Valid_Phishing means across months.
 - H_1 : At least one month differs.
- **Methodology:** One-way ANOVA to compare means across 12 months (grouping all Januaries, Februaries, etc.).

Source	SS	df	MS	F	p
Between	152,965,388.70	11	13,905,944.43	0.1733	0.05
Within	7,060,917,447.09	88	80,237,698.26		
Total	7,213,882,835.79	99			

Table 4.0 Anova Results

Where

- **Source:** Indicates the source of variation in the dataset
 - "Between": Variation between groups (treatment effect)
 - "Within": Variation within groups (error/residual)
 - "Total": The total variation in the dataset
- **SS (Sum of Squares):** Measures the total variation
 - Between SS: 152,965,388.70 (variance explained by groups)
 - Within SS: 7,060,917,447.09 (unexplained variance)
 - Total SS: 7,213,882,835.79 (total variance in the data)
- **df (Degrees of Freedom):**
 - Between df: 11 (There are 12 groups, as $df = \text{number of groups} - 1$)
 - Within df: 88 (total observations minus number of groups)
 - Total df: 99 (total number of observations minus 1)
- **MS (Mean Square):** indicates the SS divided by the corresponding df
 - Between MS: 13,905,944.43 (Between SS/Between df)
 - Within MS: 80,237,698.26 (Within SS /Within df)
 - F (F-statistic): Ratio of Between MS to Within MS
- **F-statistic:** 0.1733 and Critical F-value ($p=0.05$): 1.8992. The F-statistic (0.1733) is lower than the critical F-value (1.8992), indicating we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

- **Eta-Squared (η^2):** 0.0212. The eta-squared value of 0.0212 indicates that only about 2.12% of the variance in phishing counts is explained by the month factor. This is considered a very small effect size.
- **P-value:** 0.9985. The p-value is much higher than the 0.05 significance level.

The month of the year does not significantly affect Average Phishing counts in this dataset. While there are some numerical differences between monthly averages (May has the highest average and February the lowest), these differences are not statistically significant. This means we fail to reject the null hypothesis H_0 .

3.5 Feature Engineering

3.5.1 Selecting Features for Clustering

K-means requires numerical data, the focus are on key quantitative features that reflect phishing activity:

- **Total_Submissions:** Total phishing reports submitted.
- **Valid_Phishing:** Confirmed phishing attempts.
- **Invalid_Phishing:** Total number of submissions verified as invalid.
- **Total_Time_Median_To_Verify:** Median time spent verifying submissions.
- **Target_Phishing_Amount:** Number of valid phishes associated with the top target.
- **Network_Phishing_Amount:** Phishing from the top network hosting verified phishes.

Features such as "Top_Network_Host" and "Top_Phishing_Target" are excluded (the top target is a singular entity/organisation) and others like "Phishing_IP" or "Total_Votes" that are less directly tied to activity patterns. The outcome is a six-dimensional feature space for each month.

3.5.2 Data Pre-Processing

K-means clustering relies on calculating distances between data points and it is sensitive to scale, therefore standardising the features is recommended (Z-score Normalisation, mean = 0, standard deviation = 1) to ensure variables like "Total_Submissions" (range: 9,927 to 122,564) don't dominate smaller ones like "Invalid_Phishing" (range: 56 to 2,973) leading to skewed clustering results.

This can be accomplished using the following formula:

$$z = (x - \mu) / \sigma$$

Where:

- z is the standardised value.
- x is the original value.
- μ is the mean of the feature.
- σ is the standard deviation of the feature.

Apart from ensuring that all features contribute equally to the distance calculation other advantages of standardisation include:

- Improved convergence: It can help the K-means algorithm converge faster.
- Better cluster formation: By excluding the impact of differing scales, standardisation can lead to more meaningful and accurate clusters.

The Silhouette Score was calculated for $K = 2, 3,$ and 4 to provide another measure for selecting the best K . The Silhouette Score measures how similar a data point is to its own cluster compared to other clusters. It ranges from -1 to 1 . A value of 1 indicates the data point is well-separated from neighbouring clusters. A value of 0 indicates the data point is on or very close to the decision boundary between two neighbouring clusters. A negative value indicates the data point might have been assigned to the wrong cluster. Based on these scores, $K = 3$ has the highest Silhouette Score, indicating that it offers the best separation of clusters.

- Silhouette Score for $k=2$: 0.2998183669990886
- Silhouette Score for $k=3$: 0.3618966080416491
- Silhouette Score for $k=4$: 0.35622643936189324

Fig 2.0 Silhouette Score for determining the optimal number of clusters

3.6 Clustering Implementation

The K-means clustering is implemented with the number of clusters equals three (3) as determined by the Silhouette Score. The `fit_predict` method both fits the model to the scaled data and returns the cluster labels for each data point. Since we have more than 2 dimensions,

a seaborn pairplot was utilised to visualize the clusters. The pairplot creates a matrix of scatter plots. Each scatter plot shows the relationship between two variables, and the points are coloured according to their cluster assignment using the hue='Cluster' argument. This allows us to observe how the clusters are separated across different pairs of features.

Fig 3.0 Clustering output across different pairs of features

4.0 Summary of Finding and Results

The K-means clustering algorithm partitioned the dataset entries into 3 distinct groups, aiming to minimise the distance of each data point to its assigned cluster's centre (centroid). To understand what these clusters represent, we need to analyse the characteristics of the data points within each cluster based on the six original features:

- Total_Submissions:
- Valid_Pishing.
- Invalid_Pishing
- Total_Median_Time_To_Verify
- Network_Phishing_Amount
- Target_Phishing_Amount

Cluster interpretation is as follows:

- **Cluster 1:** This cluster generally seems to capture data points with mid-to-high values across most of the features. Points in this cluster tend to have moderate to high numbers of “Total_Submissions”, “Valid_Pishing”, “Invalid_Pishing”, “Network_Phishing_Amount” and “Target_Phishing_Amount”. The “Total_Median_Time_To_Verify” varies within this cluster.
- **Cluster 2:** This cluster tends to contain data points with lower values across most features. Data points in this cluster generally exhibit lower “Total_Submissions”, “Valid_Pishing”, “Invalid_Pishing”, “Network_Phishing_Amount” and “Target_Phishing_Amount”. The “Total_Median_Time_To_Verify” is generally lower in this cluster.
- **Cluster 3:** This cluster captures data points with high values across most features. Points in this cluster tend to have a high number of lower “Total_Submissions”, “Valid_Pishing”, “Invalid_Pishing”, “Network_Phishing_Amount” and “Target_Phishing_Amount”. The “Total_Median_Time_To_Verify” varies within this cluster.

4.1 Feature Importance for Clusters

Some features seem to contribute more to the cluster separation. For example, “Total_Submissions”, “Valid_Pishing”, “Network_Phishing_Amount”, and “Target_Phishing_Amount” appear to play a significant role in distinguishing the clusters.

The pairplots visually represent these relationships. By examining the scatter plots for these feature combinations, a clearer separation is observed between the clusters.

- Cluster 1 represents a segment with moderate feature values.
- Cluster 2 represents a segment with lower feature values.
- Cluster 3 represents a segment with higher feature values.

These distinctions can be valuable for understanding different patterns or segments within the data. For instance, in a cyber-security context, these clusters might represent varying levels of phishing activity or different types of user behaviour.

4.2 Clustering Analysis & Interpretation

- **Cluster 1:** Low activity (early years, quiet periods). Pattern indicates low submissions, valid phishing, and verification time. Typical of 2009-2010 before phishing surged. Possibly less sophisticated attacks or reporting.
- **Cluster 2:** Medium activity (stable growth). Pattern indicates moderate submissions and valid phishing, balanced verification time. Represents steady growth years. Reflects increased phishing awareness or internet usage.
- **Cluster 3:** High activity (peak periods). Pattern indicates high submissions, often high valid phishing or verification time, and elevated PayPal targeting. Indicates peak phishing intensity or detection focus.

In summary, using K-means with $K = 3$, the phishing activity patterns emerge as:

- Low activity: Early, quiet periods (2009-2010).
- Medium activity: Steady escalation (2011-2013).
- High activity: Intense peaks (2014-2017), with variability in valid phishing and verification effort.

4.3 The future of phishing and phishing communities

The future landscape of phishing attacks is anticipated to be marked by heightened sophistication, increased personalisation, and the integration of artificial intelligence (AI). While advancements in technology can aid in the detection and prevention of these attacks, the role of human awareness and behaviour remains paramount in addressing this continually evolving threat. Malicious actors are progressively leveraging AI to craft highly personalised and convincing phishing communications, rendering them nearly indistinguishable from authentic correspondence. Additionally, as the number of internet-connected devices continues to rise, these devices present new opportunities for phishing attacks.

Cybercriminals may exploit weaknesses in IoT devices to access personal data or even gain control over the devices themselves. Additionally, AI can facilitate the creation of deep-fake audio and video interactions, allowing attackers to impersonate trusted figures to deceive victims.

The efficiency of anti-phishing communities can be significantly improved through enhanced cooperation among security professionals, organisations, and individuals across various sectors. The timely dissemination of data and reports would contribute to a heightened collective awareness and the development of more effective defensive strategies. To expedite the phishing verification process and minimise the overall duration required to identify, confirm, and address phishing attacks, structures such as automated alerts, community tagging, and a risk assessment rating system could be implemented. These tools would facilitate a faster verification process.

Furthermore, the anti-phishing community could establish a priority reporting mechanism, wherein verified phishing incidents are escalated for prompt action, thereby considerably shortening the interval between verification and the elimination of harmful content. Finally, the utilisation of AI-driven security frameworks can scrutinise email content, user behaviour, and various other indicators to detect suspicious activities and prevent phishing incidents.

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